
English Language Teaching and Learning by Auto Generated Captions in Google Meet

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ABSTRACT

The significant globalization of technology and media has caused broad demand in being used in language acquisition as well. The signs show that the instructions which language teachers have been using so far need to be updated to match with education in online platforms. In spite of the great consequences that digital platforms have in renovating humans' life, there are still debates over this approach to be used for measuring language learners' perception, ability to use memory retention, and cognitive thinking. Therefore, the present paper aimed to review the previous studies in this interesting field to find empowering solutions in process of human language to achieve extensive performance in language acquisition with the help of subtitles, translation, eye-tracking method, and computing technology such as auto generated captions which could be revolutionary in connecting cognitive mind of learners with language learning. Furthermore, this paper takes into account the significant keys to improve pronunciation competence accurately and fluently since this ability is essential to produce correct captions to be understood by viewers. To this goal, technology and media have vital roles in creating appropriate environment in the classrooms that encourage both young and adult learners. Finally, we can make a conclusion that auto generated captions and online methods in education are underrated, and they would benefit both language tools developers and scholars who value cognitive mind of the learners in a lifelong learning process.

Keywords: ESL, EFL, Auto Generated Captions, Google Meet, Media.

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this article is to review the previous studies and take a closer look at the topic of teaching and learning a second or foreign language while focusing on pronunciation accuracy in the field of language education and media with auto generated subtitles used in online platforms. Learning a foreign language can be both challenging and fun. In order to emphasize on the fun aspect, learning needs to happen in an enjoyable environment, so that it could benefit learners and satisfy them while spending time in the classrooms. Language education has experienced several obstacles in the past two decades to promote a high level of cognitive thinking. With a growth in digital world and technology, learners became tired of traditional methods in teaching and demanded a change. Following the increasing population of internet users, gamers, and social media

developers, language teachers had to keep up with this fast-paced wave and start using modern tools in the classrooms. Education and media are moving forward hand in hand, so it is better to accept the revolutionary change from traditional methods of teaching to a more technology friendly one.

The most recent obstacle that education faced was Covid-19 pandemic. It caused schools, universities, private institutes, etc. to shut down; therefore, teachers were left with no choice except using digital platforms. In English as a second or foreign language (ESL/EFL) teachers tried to provide materials in shape of videos, slides, online language game websites, etc. to make sure that language learners did not feel bored or uninterested by just looking at a screen at home. In other words, ESL/EFL teachers' job became even harder compared to face-to-face classrooms, because lots of teaching materials had to be developed again to be suitable for online education. Teachers had to create an online environment symmetrical to what learners used to experience before in the sense of having the same rules and vibes. [12] defines it as "when teaching is successful, the minds of students resonate with each other, and all together they resonate with that of the teacher; bodies, in this circumstance, become the quasi mystical incarnation of a symphony of minds" (p. 54). This is probably the final product equivalent to complete attention that a teacher is looking for in online platforms. At the beginning, managing an online class seemed impossible to few teachers who did not have any experiences in working with digital tools. With that being said, we cannot deny the fact that after holding workshops for them, they were mostly satisfied with what technology offered to the humanities, education and psychology fields. The most important advantage of using media was that it changed the perspective of students and showed them that learning a language does not necessarily mean only repeating after teachers or waiting for teachers' feedback. Using media and online platforms helped students in intermediate and advanced levels to start working on their English knowledge on their own while enjoying the peaceful atmosphere of home. In low proficiency level, English Language learners face difficulties in memorization of new vocabulary, pronunciation of them, and using them in correct grammar structures while speaking or writing. There is a need for an instructor to be present in order to guide them in the right path [27]. This need would slowly diminish in higher proficiency levels to a point that ESL/EFL students can completely feel confident in finding and removing their own mistakes, also known as self-correction.

In language acquisition, online teaching showed us a new side of how to deliver information that can be easier to understand, because the new generation of learners is more enthusiastic about using technology in their lessons. Having a device such as your cellphone, laptop, and tablet to search for meanings and translation while watching movies, using an app to chat with foreigners, and listening to new songs while looking at their lyrics in the internet are all activities which are now easily possible thanks to social media. This is why we believe technology can be beneficial for teaching and learning in ESL/EFL, moreover online methods of language acquisition would hold the power to keep the development of class dynamic, flexible and student-centered [6].

In this paper, we want to provide ESL/EFL learners a brighter vision in pronunciation practice for boosting up their accuracy while speaking in English language with having auto generated captions on, because it is believed that captions have the potential value in

improving the language acquisition process by providing the key to a higher level of comprehension in language input [28]. Moreover, it is possible to show students how to enhance their ability in uttering words with higher amount of accuracy such as words with similar sound parts (homophones and homographs) or the ones that create confusion in learning for example “bear” (noun), “bear” (verb), and “bare” (adjective). For this purpose, auto generated captions in online meeting platforms is the tool that we are going to discuss more about in the next section.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Education and Google Meet Platform

Scholars believe that captions have the power that is needed to link an audience to the motion pictures [1]. Having captions on the screen is a great option that technology facilitates in multimedia to help non-native language learners in education. When videos include abstract visions or complex cultural points, having captions can be helpful to get the overall point of the speech [15]. It is accessible in platforms such as YouTube, Zoom, and Google Meet, so educators are just one click away from better comprehension of speech. If you watch a video with turning the captions on, you will understand the gist of it faster. In online conferences and lectures students always face disconnection which can be really frustrating; so, it is required to turn on the auto generated captions to make sure the general ideas and the purpose of the meetings are understood well. Google Meet is an accessible virtual platform for teachers and pupils to test online captions method of teaching. Some scholars presented their studies on Google Meet in education and each recorded a list of pros and cons after interviewing students. These studies showed that advantages of using Google Meet were more than what they expected in creating an enjoyable environment for learning [14, 21, 29].

Captioned videos are suitable not only for language acquisition, but of course for people who suffer from hearing loss or the ones who are hard in hearing. This is a thoughtful way to help them feel included in online education, and make sure that they are able to communicate in classes like everyone else. Google Meet introduced close captions for live calls to its users for the first time in 2021 to help bridge language distances. As [19] suggests, Google Meet can improve students’ motivation. This motivational aspect is only a small portion of what Google Company has provided for us. This company has empowered itself by developing different types of gadgets like Google Mail, Google Calendar, Google Maps, Google Assistant, etc. to help people have an easier way in managing their education and work life [8].

The advantages of auto generated captions do not end here. It can also help native speakers in studying the videos that teachers provide for extra practice, and by turning the captions on it will aid them in note taking process [8]. YouTube as one of the first platforms to encourage automatic captions for media developers, mentioned that they used

special algorithms that are called automatic speech recognition (ASR), but it followed some shortcomings while adding subtitles to the live audiovisual contents. These shortcomings happened due to mispronunciation, foreigners' accents, dialects, or background noises. In here, the role of accurate pronunciation can be highlighted to make sure the produced subtitles do not suffer from incorrect information. Non-native teachers and media developers, who need to use live captions in their work, have to practice very much and eliminate any sort of background noises to make sure what they are saying could be recognized by the auto generated machine. Furthermore, ESL/EFL learners need to pay extra attention to their speech, since mistakes in pronunciation can result in wrong captions which lead to confusion in the mind of the listeners. [5] suggested English learners to work on learning the sounds while uttering homophones, vowels and consonants, stressing and also voice or voice-less sounds in order to block any kinds of mispronunciation.

In sound-sensitive environments, it is better to use captions when audio is not available such as in a noisy train, library, office, crowded street, and late at night when everybody else is asleep. This is a convenient way to watch something that you like without audio and still be able to understand it [13].

2.2 Previous Studies on Teaching and Language with Subtitles

At the beginning, it is important to know about different types of subtitles and how translation from L2 to L1 or vice versa could affect ESL/EFL students' acquisition of a language. When we try to look at subtitles during a film to practice our language skills, technically we are connecting psycholinguistic literature, audiovisual translation, and memory retention in order to achieve cognitive mechanism. Subtitles can be used in two forms called standard and reversed. By standard we mean a foreign language audiovisual performance with translated subtitles in the native language of viewers. Reversed subtitles are formed when the original audiovisual performance is in native viewers' language and the subtitles are seen in the foreign language. The key question is that which model (standard or reversed) would be right one to use in language teaching and learning.

Many scholars provided rich results regarding to using captions while watching films. [3] believed that English language learners can learn better if the audiovisual tools which teachers use in classes have captions. Captioned media can improve vocabulary acquisition, listening comprehension, and word recognition; moreover, it can teach unfamiliar words in both spoken and written versions, so we should use our hearing and sight abilities at the same time. Psychologists think that when we see the words displayed on the screen and hearing them at the same time means using two senses together which increases the process of learning and this can be true even for people who are hard in hearing. A study in US by [24] showed that how close captions benefited more than 2000 students (regarding to students with any kind of hearing disabilities and the ones who did not have any disabilities). The findings showed that more than half of the population of participants used close captions in their educational practice videos that they use to understand the lessons better at least sometimes. They agreed on the fact that using captions helped them to focus and retain information and overcome the poor audio quality

in some videos. Even students with no hearing difficulty found captions useful in comprehension of lessons.

Learning in digital era plus captions in videos can motivate language learners in participating in the class more than traditional tools [7, 22]. There is a significant positive view about using captions in audiovisual forms to enhance comprehension. Subtitle reading works in favor of language learning, but it is essential to be aware of the length and size of the lines. A study by [11] showed that reading subtitles can be helpful in language classes only if the length of subtitle is reduced to keep the attention of learners on all three aspects of a video including subtitles, audios and the moving pictures.

One of the issues that ESL/EFL learners experience is when they try to watch a movie or listen to a dialogue; however, the conversations are fast-speed and hard to comprehend. Most teachers hear their students complain about this problem and the fact that they think the speech does not have a normal speed. Their ears are not used to listening skills at higher levels, so they find it challenging to keep up with the speakers. As [10] suggested, close captions make it easier to follow along with the speech; furthermore, they could help with dialogue that is spoken quickly or the ones that include unfamiliar brand names and technical terminology.

An interesting study by [23] showed that fifty Japanese EFL students benefited from using automatic subtitles in their oral test. According to him, YouTube could be a helpful platform to objectively measure EFL students' speaking performances. Subjective oral tests done by teachers were different since humans can comprehend the meaning and form of a sentence quicker than speaker's speed in speech and if a word was pronounced wrong, the teacher could guess it without any problems; therefore, a new system was provided to get scores based on how good the actual speech is. In the data collection procedure, the researcher employed YouTube platform's ASR engine to score students' oral performance. The audiovisual files of each student's speaking test was uploaded on YouTube, ASR engine was activated, and finally the researcher could transcribe students' speaking based on what was recognized and produced as captions on the screen. This method also eliminated any sort of situations that a biased student would be offered a higher mark by the teacher.

Another research related to reading speed of subtitles and how it influenced cognitive comprehension was piloted by Polish scholars [26]. In this study they used six-second rule in speed of displaying subtitles on the screen. The procedure included showing 53 Polish viewers an English film with Polish subtitle with two different speech rates (slow and fast). Results showed that the speech rate affected the comprehension of viewers. Faster dialogues which meant more text in the subtitle during the six seconds resulted in lower comprehension of the film's story plot compared to slower rate of speech with the same situation in subtitle. This paper also analyzed the eye movements of the viewers during the process of watching the film, and it was found that viewers with higher level of English proficiency spent less time (only 30%) looking at the subtitles displayed on the screen.

2.3 Eye-tracking in Language Learning

In the next step, there is a need to review studies which used scientific methods such as Eye-tracking in applied linguistics and articles about the topic of reading subtitles for improvement in language acquisition. Many bright scholars tried to employ eye-tracking method while students were completing an audiovisual activity like watching a film [2, 16, 31, 25, 20]. According to these scholars, eye-tracking is the main way to look into the mind of a learner, because it is connected to reading behavior and viewing visual features. A study with English and French bilinguals as participants showed that displaying a group of images (with their French translation under them) while listening to an English sentence in audio version that involved one of the images in itself, could quickly change the eye movement of participants. Eye-tracking showed that they looked at the vocabulary in French on the screen, then the photo, and tried to make sense of what they have heard in English to choose the correct photo. The difficulty involved with some words that could have two meaning in French language; so choosing the correct image was only possible if they could guess the English word's translation correctly based on the pragmatics aspect of the sentence [4].

Eye-tracking can be connected to study of semiotics of face as well. We should include this version of semiotics to investigate visual attention to instructors in online video effect in education. Moreover, perceptions of pupils and recording their face while learning in class will mean taking one step further than just studying the eyes and going beyond to other facial expressions. An eye-tracking analysis performed by [30] aimed to discover how instructor's presence in online videos affected learning process and learners' perceptions about situational interest of class and their judgment of learning structures. Two videos were used to test the visual attention of 60 college students. One video showed the instructor as the presenter in the lesson and the other one was with an already made content that did not involve a human instructor face, only a narrator's voice. The results showed improvement in learning topics by instructor as the teacher on the screen. Students liked the transfer of information being done by a human face rather than just listening to the audio explaining the lesson. Furthermore, this method increased students' satisfaction and situational interest in an online class.

A recent study by [9] compared the possible impacts of professional and automatic captions (auto generated captions) on video watching experience. This study promoted human-centered computing and sound-recognition technology in captioning. For the methodology, the scholars used three types of videos from YouTube which all included standard American English, dialogues, and had both professional and automatic captions. The key element in data analysis was the use of eye-tracking based on a study by [18]. The results after running a survey with multiple-choice and open-ended questions showed that viewers had a better retention in answering the questions which were about plot and characters' names by watching the professional captions. They also could answer matching section of the questionnaire which was about connecting face of the characters to the right names with the purpose of measuring their visual-sense in recognizing screenshots of important scenes of the videos. The survey was designed to rate viewers' emotional engagement as well. The findings showed that 75% of viewers voted for watching a video with professional captions; however, it did not mean they disagreed with automatic

captions. Professional videos include sound-captions, soundtrack names, and characters' feelings in them, so it helped viewers to emotionally focus more on the plot of the video. This can mean that in the future, automatic captions need to level up and ASR machine needs to have more sensitive sensors to recognize sounds produced by speakers.

Finally, studies on English language teaching and learning with an in depth focus on auto generated captions are still being developed. We need to spend more time on fostering articles and experiments on this issue to enhance proficiency levels in ESL/EFL education in online platforms. As it was mentioned before, technology is playing an important part in education at the moment with creating enjoyable environment for young and adult learners, so it is wiser to go forward and look upon a brighter vision for our learners in the future. As [17] suggested, we still have a long way to trust media platforms in the educational systems, but with more practice and advancement in digital humanities a better online class can be provided soon. Also, a major drawback that was found during working with auto generated captions by the researcher of this article is related to words that are sometimes misspelled in Google Meet such as “pick” and “peck”. If each of these words is pronounced individually once, the chance of them being recognized and typed by auto generated captions is very low. Despite the fact that the pronunciation is still accurate, it seems that Google Meet can understand and separate the difference 100% only if they are used in a sentence. The machine is capable of recognizing the term based on the general meaning of the whole sentence. This issue has to be experimented and solved in the further studies.

3. CONCLUSION

At last, we can come to this point that using subtitles can be seen in education of both native and non-native students. The primary goal for researchers is to connect education with scientific methods such as language acquisition studies and eye-tracking method to enhance learning in students with disabilities. However, this process is still not complete and needs extra amount of experiments to promote a valuable conclusion. Media added many positive features to education and ESL/EFL teachers need to be updated in using the recent methods in online classes. Google Meet is a great platform that is being used all around the world to make connection easier for everyone. Since 2021, auto generated captions in Google Meet increased the public satisfaction, because using captions during video conferences or lecture can benefit learners in higher comprehension of the topic in hand. It is highly recommended to use subtitles in ESL/EFL teaching and learning as well. The studies showed that subtitles could actually benefit all kinds of learners (native, non-native, with disabilities) to process and digest their lessons easier and faster.

REFERENCES

- [1] Basaran, H. F. & Kose, G. D. (2012). The Effects of Captioning on EFL Learners' Listening Comprehension. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 70, p. 702-708.

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- [2] Bisson, M. J., Van Heuven, W. J., Conklin, K., & Tunney, R. J. (2014). Processing of Native and Foreign Language Subtitles in Films: An Eye Tracking Study. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, vol. 35, no. 2, p. 399-418.
- [3] Brann, A. (2011). Captioning to Support Literacy. Readingrockets. <https://www.readingrockets.org/article/captioning-support-literacy-0>
- [4] Chambers, C. G., & Cooke, H. (2009). Lexical Competition during Second-language Listening: Sentence Context, but Not Proficiency, Constrains Interference from the Native Lexicon. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, vol. 35, no. 4, 1029.
- [5] Devika, S. C. (2022). The Accuracy of Auto-generated Subtitles of Four Indonesian English-speaking Youtubers (Doctoral dissertation, Widya Mandala Surabaya Catholic University).
- [6] Dhawan, S. (2020). Online Learning: A Panacea in the Time of COVID-19 Crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, vol. 49, p. 5-22.
- [7] Evmenova, A. S. (2008). Lights! Camera! Captions! The Effects of Picture and/or Word Captioning Adaptations, Alternative Narration, and Interactive Features on Video Comprehension by Students with Intellectual Disabilities (Doctoral dissertation, George Mason University).
- [8] Ismail, N. S., Ahmad, N. Z., Fauzi, A., & Mohd, K. N. (2021). The Use of Google Meet in Learning Arabic Language during Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of e-Learning and Higher Education (IJELHE)*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 4-19.
- [9] Kim, H., Tao, Y., Liu, C., Zhang, Y. & Li, Y. (2023). Comparing the Impact of Professional and Automatic Closed Captions on Video-Watching Experience. In Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA '23), April 23–28, 2023. Hamburg, Germany. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 6 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544549.3585634>
- [10] Klein, R. (2022). Are You Captioning Your Meetings? 3playmedia. <https://www.3playmedia.com/blog/are-you-captioning-your-meetings/>
- [11] Kruger, J. L., & Steyn, F. (2014). Subtitles and Eye Tracking: Reading and Performance. *Reading Research Quarterly*, vol. 49, no. 1, p. 105-120.
- [12] Leone, M. (2021). Face-to-Face: The Semiotics of Online Teaching (or, in Praise of the Classroom). *Language and Semiotic Studies*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 34-56.
- [13] Lewis, E. (2022). 8 Benefits of Video Transcription & Captioning. 3playmedia. <https://www.3playmedia.com/blog/8-benefits-of-transcribing-captioning-videos/>
- [14] Lý, T. (2021). The Practice of English Teaching and Learning with Google Meet From Non-English Major Students View. In VietTESOL International Convention Proceedings.
- [15] Markham, P. (2001). The Influence of Culture-specific Background Knowledge and Captions on Second Language Comprehension. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, vol. 29, no. 4, p. 331-344.
- [16] Montero Perez, M., Peters, E., & Desmet, P. (2015). Enhancing Vocabulary Learning through Captioned Video: An Eye-tracking Study. *The Modern Language Journal*, vol. 99, no. 2, p. 308-328.
- [17] Parton, B. (2016). Video Captions for Online Courses: Do YouTube's Auto-generated Captions Meet Deaf Students' Needs? *Journal of Open, Flexible and Distance Learning*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 8-18.
- [18] Perego, E., Orrego-Carmona, D., & Bottiroli, S. (2016). An empirical take on the

-
- dubbing vs. subtitling debate: an eye movement study. *Lingue e Linguaggi*, vol. 19, p. 255-274.
- [19] Putra, R. W. P. (2021). Improving the Students' Motivation in Learning English through Google Meet during the Online Learning. *English Learning Innovation (englie)*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 35-42.
- [20] Ragni, V. (2020). More than Meets the Eye. An Eye-tracking Study on the Effects of Translation on the Processing and Memorization of Reversed Subtitles. *The Journal of Specialized Translation*, vol. 33, p. 99-128.
- [21] Sarwar, N. (2021). How Google Meet's New Features Benefit Students & Teachers. ScreenRant. <https://screenrant.com/google-meets-new-education-featuresstudent-teacher-benefits/>
- [22] Shea, P. (2000). Leveling the Playing Field: A Study of Captioned Interactive Video for Second Language Learning. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 22, no. 3, p. 243-263.
- [23] Spring, R. (2020). Using Multimedia Tools to Objectively Rate the Pronunciation of L1 Japanese EFL Learners. *ATEM Journal*, vol. 25, p. 113-124.
- [24] Stritto, M. E. D. & Linder, K. (2017). A Rising Tide: How Closed Captions Can Benefit All Students. Educause. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2017/8/a-rising-tide-how-closed-captions-can-benefit-all-students>
- [25] Suvorov, R. (2015). The Use of Eye Tracking in Research on Video-based Second Language (L2) Listening Assessment: A Comparison of Context Videos and Content Videos. *Language Testing*, vol. 32, no. 4, p. 463-483.
- [26] Szarkowska, A., & Bogucka, L. (2019). Six-second Rule Revisited: An Eye-tracking Study on the Impact of Speech Rate and Language Proficiency on Subtitle Reading. *Translation. Cognition & Behavior*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 101-124.
- [27] Taylor, J. R. (2002). *Cognitive Grammar*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- [28] Vanderplank, R. (1988). The Value of Teletext Sub-titles in Language Learning. *ELT Journal*, vol. 42, no. 4, p. 272-281.
- [29] Wahyuni, A. (2021). Students' Perceptions of Using Google Meet in Learning English as Foreign Language at Muhammadiyah University of Makassar (Master's thesis, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar).
- [30] Wang, J., Antonenko, P., & Dawson, K. (2020). Does Visual Attention to the Instructor in Online Video Affect Learning and Learner Perceptions? An Eye-tracking Analysis. *Computers & Education*, vol. 146, 103779.
- [31] Winke, P., Gass, S., & Sydorenko, T. (2013). Factors Influencing the Use of Captions by Foreign Language Learners: An Eye-tracking Study. *The Modern language journal*, vol. 97, no. 1, p. 254-275.
- [32] Wisniewska, N. & Mora, J. C. (2018). Pronunciation Learning through Captioned Videos. In J. Levis (Ed.), Proceedings of the 9th Pronunciation in Second Language Learning and Teaching conference, ISSN 2380-9566, University of Utah, September, 2017 (pp. 204-215). Ames, IA: Iowa State University.